

DiSSCo Transition Project

Plan for integration of the Collection Digitisation Dashboard with the core infrastructure and connection with Latimer Core compatible data sources for collection descriptions

Work Package Data Infrastructure & Core Services Milestone 15

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Plan for integration of the Collection

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Executive Summary

The following report evaluates the status of implemented Collections Digitisation Dashboard in the DiSSCo RI leveraging on a blueprint developed in the ICEDIG project. Building on this assessment, an integration and extension plan starting from the static (e.g. google sheet based) implementations towards a continuously updating source of information for DSArch, DiSSCo's core Digital Specimen architecture is outlined. Particular emphasis is placed on the alignment with relevant semantic artefacts to describe collections and the state of digitization such as Latimer Core and MIDS.

Keywords

Collections Digitisation Dashboard, Digital Specimen Architecture, Latimer Core, Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen, FAIR

List of abbreviations

CA - Consortium Agreement
CETAF - Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities
CDD - Collection Digitisation Dashboard
D - Deliverable
DiSSCo - Distributed System of Scientific Collections
DSArch - Digital Specimen Architecture
DTP - DiSSCo Transition Project
FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GA - Grant Agreement
GBIF - Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GrSciColl - Global Registry of Scientific Collections
MS - Milestone
RFC - Request For Comments
RI - Research Infrastructure
WP - Work Package

1. Introduction

The concept of a Collections Digitisation Dashboard (CDD) was developed during the ICEDIG project (Casino et al, 2019). It aimed to provide a broad, structured, visual summary of collections digitisation, along with other indicators, that together would allow strategic planning, increase discoverability, enable prioritisation and identify specialisation.

Continued in SYNTHESYS+, a major objective of the further CDD development was to display the key metrics linked to the MIDS specification which defined elements required for various levels of digitisation (Haston 2023). These metrics are essential for guiding further decisions and navigating the content of DiSSCo's collections. A significant aspect when making data of physical specimens, derived material samples and their relations digitally available, is the tight integration with the FAIRification of these data, i.e. make these data (semi-) autonomously processable by machines, a feature that's termed "machine-actionability" (Jacobsen 2020). Adoption and usage of MIDS and the related specification for collections descriptions called Latimer Core (LtC, Woodburn 2022) provide objective measures of FAIR compliance, making the CDD an essential tool for monitoring, measuring and analysing digitisation progress in all process steps from initial data capturing to subsequent annotation and mobilisation.

2. Overview of existing prototype CDD solutions

This section provides an overview of the implementation and data sources of three existing CDD solutions that may serve to some degree as a blueprint for an integrated DiSSCo CDD.

2.1 SYNTHESYS+ Collections Digitisation Dashboard (CDD)

The SYNTHESYS+ Collections Digitisation Dashboard (<https://rebrand.ly/synth-cdd>) was a proof of concept, developing the scope and structure of the data (including controlled vocabularies) and data visualisations to support the DiSSCo use cases defined in the ICEDIG project and refined as part of SYNTHESYS+. Nine European institutions that were partners in SYNTHESYS+ provided data for the proof of concept, the data and dashboards for which are currently hosted by NHM London (Tiley 2024).

Implementation

Data for the dashboard were collected using a structured Google Sheets template ([example](#)), with a copy provided to each participating institution. Once completed, these spreadsheets were saved locally in Excel format and subject to manual validation to detect and resolve issues. VBA code was used to generate the appropriate SQL INSERT statements to import the data into a central database, and post-import data quality control checks were then run against the data in the database.

The dashboard itself was developed using Microsoft Power BI, and is currently hosted in the NHM, London's Power BI service. It connects directly to the underlying database, refactoring the structure of the data in Power BI to support the data visualisations.

Dashboard data can be refreshed from the database on demand, but both the data and the dashboard have been static since the SYNTHESYS+ project ended. The dashboard has no access restrictions, and in addition to being accessible directly is also currently embedded in the DiSSCo and CETAF websites.

Data structure

The CDD database is a MySQL relational database, with the schema based substantially on the version of the draft Latimer Core standard and model available at that time (2020). Further information on the data model and schema can be found in [Tilley et al, 2024](#). The schema has remained static since implementation, and doesn't reflect the further development of Latimer Core from 2020 up to ratification in 2024.

The data represent effectively four different breakdowns of each institution's collections: a high level breakdown at discipline level, and three more detailed breakdowns by classification and geographic location, storage or chronostratigraphy. Within these breakdowns, every combination represents a collection component to which metrics (object counts and MIDS level assessments) are attached. As these represent the same collections being broken down multiple times in parallel, they were separated in the database into multiple collection description schemes (precursors to [Latimer Core Schemes](#) in LtC) to ensure that the same objects are not counted more than once in dashboard aggregations. Each collection component in each breakdown is modelled as a distinct LtC ObjectGroup to which data (including the CDD metrics) can be attached. This 'dimensional' approach is well suited to supporting dashboard visualisations and aggregations, and also makes it easy to extend the data attached to each collection component in the future if required.

As described above, MIDS level assessments (as percentages) are one of the metrics attached to the CDD collections breakdowns. The definitions of the MIDS levels used were those available at that time (2020), and have been further developed since, so a new implementation of the CDD would need to take that into account.

2.2 DiSSCo UK Implementation

The DiSSCo UK collection survey was first rolled out in 2021, surveying a total of 88 UK natural science institutions in the DiSSCo UK network and exposing the data and insights through a public dashboard (accessible directly [here](#), or via the [DiSSCo UK website](#)). The initiative was coordinated by Tara Wainwright, DiSSCo UK Community Analyst at the NHM, London.

Implementation

Data was collected from the participating institutions using a macro-enabled Excel spreadsheet template, based on the CDD Google sheet structure and layout with some minor modifications. These included some changes related to the data captured (see

below), and some functionality (coded in VBA) to conditionally show and hide worksheets. Each institution completed and returned a copy of the template.

The dashboard was developed using Microsoft Power BI, and is currently hosted in the NHM, London's Power BI service alongside the CDD dashboard. It pulls data directly from the submitted Excel files in a Sharepoint folder, and the data are aggregated across all sheets and refactored to support the visualisations using the Power Query functionality within Power BI. This approach was intended to make the incorporation of new or updated templates easy in the future without the need for technical expertise. Dashboard data can be refreshed from the source spreadsheets on demand, and although the data and dashboard have been largely static since the survey initially completed in 2022, a small number of additional institutions have been incorporated since that point.

The survey team also took the default approach of creating records in GRSciColl on the behalf of each participating institution if they didn't already exist (although there was a flag in the template allowing participants to opt out if preferred).

Data structure

The DiSSCo UK survey data design was based on that used by the SYNTHESYS+ CDD, using the same collections breakdowns and metrics, and largely the same controlled vocabularies. The one exception to the latter was the geographic location vocabulary, which was simplified from the 26 terrestrial and marine regions used in the CDD to just 'terrestrial' and 'marine', after consultation with DiSSCo UK stakeholders. The institutional information fields in the template were also expanded to ensure that all data required to create GRSciColl records were captured. Additionally, the DiSSCo survey used updated MIDS level definitions, as these had changed since the SYNTHESYS+ CDD was constructed.

Although the DiSSCo UK data aren't stored in a database, the aligned structure of the template with the CDD means that they still conform to the same data model. The downside of using the templates as a direct data source rather than a database however is that querying and extracting the data across the whole dataset is at present a more complex process.

2.3 DiSSCo Flanders Implementation

In 2022 a survey was conducted to retrieve high-level data on the natural science collections managed by the 14 institutes that are part of the DiSSCo Flanders consortium. This resulted in complete data records for 8 of the institutes.

The initiative was coordinated by Ann van Baelen and Nathalie Poot (KU Leuven, Scientific Collections & Heritage department). In 2023, Lissa Breugelmans and Maarten Trekels (Botanic Garden Meise) processed the data as part of an implementation exercise for the newly developed [Latimer Core](#) standard and developed a public dashboard showcasing the Flemish collections. The dashboard is directly accessible through [this link](#) and integrated into the [DiSSCo Flanders GBIF hosted portal](#).

Implementation

Data was collected from the institutes using an Excel survey based on the survey developed for SYNTHESYS+ (see 2.1). In contrast to the original survey, DiSSCo Flanders collections also include living collections as well as tissue- and DNA-samples. Therefore, changes to the original templates were implemented to adapt to this kind of data (see details below).

The raw survey results were saved locally and the data was extracted, pivoted into a vertical format and processed using a Microsoft Power Query script and aggregated across the institution sheets. A data model for a MySQL database was developed, with table and attribute names corresponding to Latimer Core terms. The aggregated data was imported into the MySQL database after mapping the column names to Latimer Core terms and splitting the data into multiple sheets, corresponding to the MySQL database tables.

A dashboard was developed using Microsoft PowerBI, which is currently hosted in Meise Botanic Garden's PowerBI service. For ease of implementation, the current version of the dashboard is connected to the flat file with the processed and aggregated survey data. The data and dashboard have been static since the survey was completed in 2022, although new data can be amended or updated and the dashboard will automatically reflect this.

Data Structure

The DiSSCo Flanders survey design was based on the original SYNTHESYS+ survey, although it was adapted to allow collecting data on (1) not just preserved collections, but also living collections (e.g. botanical gardens, zoos) and tissue and DNA samples, and (2) for each individual natural science collection housed within an institute. The survey design is described in [Van Baelen et al. \(2022\)](#).

The database model that was developed is published as an implementation experience report (see [Breugelmans and Trekels, 2023a](#) and [Breugelmans and Trekels, 2023b](#)). Access to the original data remains restricted under GDPR law.

A new round of the inventory exercise is planned for 2024 and the survey design will be updated, to reflect i.a. the updated [ODS ontology](#) and complete the data collection for all institutes. This will also reflect the effort done by the institutes to map out more carefully the housed collections.

3. Integration Plan with DiSSCo

To move the CDD from a static dashboard into a continuously updating source of information, we need to integrate the CDD with the broader DiSSCo Digital Specimen architecture. At the moment, the CDD implementations contain static metadata about the

collections. This data is often gathered through one time surveys. This data gives a vital image into information such as the estimated collection size.

However, we would like to combine the estimated information for collections (i.e. above specimen-level) with the specimen-level information from the digitised portion of collections. This digitised information can be found in DiSSCo where it has been collected from the institutional Collection Management Systems and harmonised to a collective data standard called open Digital Specimen (openDS, Islam 2020). The digital information in DiSSCo consists of metadata about the specimen and any associated media. During data ingestion, for each specimen the Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen (MIDS) is calculated and added to the specimen information.¹

By combining digitised information and collection metadata we can provide a rich overview in which we can indicate what portion of the collection has been digitised and is available through DiSSCo and what the MIDS level of the digitisation is but also summarise and make discoverable the parts of collections that are yet to be digitised. We can create different drilldowns for different topic disciplines, taxonomic groups and many more. The next sections detail how we want to develop this solution and what the technical requirements are.

3.1 From pilot to production

The pilot developed in SYNTHESYS+ does not yet make use of the DiSSCo core infrastructure. It currently includes only collections from a few institutions. To develop the pilot further into a mature DiSSCo services a number of things are needed:

- Integration with the core infrastructure is needed to fulfil the requirements of the DiSSCo DMP, including the requirement that all specimen related data should be served as FAIR Digital Object (FDO) and be FAIR.
- Integration is also needed to scale up to data from all DiSSCo partners, the current implementation requires a manual import process. This needs to be automated using the core infrastructure REST APIs and requires implementation of a (semi-automated) editorial process through CETAF to get additional data and keep it up to date. Given that the number of DiSSCo institutions could grow to >500, national nodes will need a role in this in the future.
- To scale up to list hundreds of institutions and collections changes in the pilot user interface are needed such as select options to select a particular institution or collection.
- The work on controlled vocabularies and standardisation of collection descriptions has advanced since the pilot (DiSSCo vocabularies such as openDS, Latimer Core and MIDS) and the CDD needs to be adjusted to these developments.
- The information about non-digitised parts of the collection needs to be combined with information about digitised parts, using data from DiSSCo digital specimens.
- There is a wish from the community to re-use data from existing collection descriptions, in particular CETAF registry, GrSciColl and Index Herbariorum (IH). Institutions should be able to choose these as their source system, however

¹ Haston et al. 2023.

additional collection metadata may be needed for the CDD that is not in GrSciColl and IH and data in GrSciColl may need to be updated to use required vocabularies.

- There is a wish from the community to implement national CDDs. Countries making use of a GBIF hosted portal could achieve this through that tooling, but for other countries it may be beneficial if the CDD could be installed and configured as a national CDD. It needs to be investigated if the current tooling (Microsoft BI) is suitable for that or if a different solution is needed for the CDD frontend.

3.2 Production CDD architecture

The architecture of the Collection Digitisation Dashboard is based on the integration with the Digital Specimen Architecture (DSArch) (Leefflang et al. 2022). We will reuse components that are already developed for the DSArch and follow the same guidelines. We decoupled the architecture for the CDD into four main components, harvesting data from existing collection registries, data storage and an interface layer and the frontend. Together, they form an extensible and scalable solution for the storage and display of the collection information. A graphical overview of this envisioned architecture is given in Fig. 1.

Data Harvesting

At the moment, there are several locations where collection metadata exists (Hobern et al. 2023). Instead of DiSSCo creating an additional collection registry, we would rather collect all existing information and, if needed, provide the user the possibility to add DiSSCo specific information. This would ensure that users don't need to duplicate the data but can have one location where they add and edit their records (apart from metadata needed by DiSSCo that is not supported in an existing collection registry).

This means that we need to build a collection metadata harvesting application. GrSciColl is a global aggregator of existing collection registries, so data can be harvested from GrSciColl. Data from CETAF Registry does not need to be harvested if it is transformed in a CETAF-DiSSCo registry that stores data directly in DSArch. The application would run over GrSciColl and collect the collection metadata. It needs to run regularly as information might get updated in the source data set.

During the harvesting, we will also translate the collected data into a harmonised data model based on Latimer Core. This will ensure that all data within the DiSSCo infrastructure will have the same data model and can easily be indexed and served. Only collection metadata will be harvested from records that have been marked as source in GrSciColl by collection providers. If no record was marked as source then the CETAF-DiSSCo record will be treated as source and DiSSCo will provide GrSciColl with collection metadata from the CETAF-DiSSCo registry which is then the source system for GrSciColl.

Data storage

For the data storage, we will reuse the storage layer of DSArch, described in detail in BiCIKL deliverable 7.4 (Theocharides et al. 2024). The DSArch storage layer consists of three components. The latest active record will be stored in a relational database where it will be easily accessible and persistently stored. The data will not be fully normalised, only fields necessary to indicate relationships will be separately stored, the rest of the information will be stored as JavaScript Object Notation (JSON).² To fully index all fields in the JSON, we use an indexing solution. This indexing solution provides capabilities for complex searches and aggregations.

Each digital object within the DSArch will have a provenance record. Whenever an object changes, a change event is generated which can be pushed to external infrastructures but is also captured by a provenance service. This provenance service stores the new version of the object as well as the specific changes with the previous version of the object using JSON patch.³ This gives us the possibility to go back to previous versions, as well as recreate the object from the changes. As collection metadata will be part of the DSArch, this functionality will also be available for the collections.

Interface layer

To expose the collection information, we create a set of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). These RESTful APIs will be based on the API recommendation as published in Deliverable 1.3 of the BiCIKL project (Addink et al. 2023). Within an API, we will combine aggregated information from the Digital Specimen with the Collection Metadata. The data format through which we will expose this information will be based on Latimer Core. Filtering options will be available to select collections from specific countries, organisations, topic disciplines, etc...

In addition to data retrieval endpoints, we will also develop a range of endpoints through which authenticated and authorised users or applications can add additional information to a collection object. This new information will create a new version of the collection object and trigger a change event, resulting in a provenance record. The change event could also be sent to external infrastructures.

Frontend

The summaries of the current existing CDDs in the previous chapter indicate there is a clear need for a generic dashboard. However, they also indicate that there are organisational, regional and national differences required in the dashboards. By decoupling the storage from the frontend with the interface layer, we create the possibility to have multiple different applications using the same interface layer. Essential for this to work is to have a clear interface based on accepted standards from the Biodiversity Data Standards (TDWG) and good documentation based on the OpenAPI specification.⁴

² For this we use the *jsonb* Column from PostgreSQL, <https://www.postgresql.org/docs/16/datatype-json.html> (Visited on 15-04-2024)

³ <https://jsonpatch.com/> (Visited on 15-04-2024)

⁴ <https://www.openapis.org/> (Visited on 16-04-2024)

DiSSCo will provide a generic dashboard which will encompass all connected countries. However, it would be helpful if this generic implementation can easily be customised for specific solutions. An approach such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) hosted portal might be an interesting solution.⁵ To create a specific implementation of the CDD, users could fork the generic solution and use that as a template. They would then be able to change logos, colours and select specific default filtering options.

Figure 1: Schematic overview of the information flow in the envisioned CDD architecture integrated with DS Arch.

4. Further technical requirements and Outlook

This section will dig deeper into some of the technical requirements which we will need to tackle before the CDD can be developed. Some of these requirements are essential to have at the start of the development, we will discuss those first, others can be refined later.

Collection identifier

Essential to the functioning of the CDD and the integration with DiSSCo is to have a globally unique collection identifier as part of the specimen data. When this collection identifier is not part of the specimen data, DiSSCo will have no possibility of connecting the specimen to a collection and cannot create any metrics regarding the digitisation effort. We need to decide what identifier we will use for collections and make the importance of including it in the specimen information clear to the institutions.

⁵ <https://www.gbif.org/hosted-portals> (Visited on 16-04-2024)

DiSSCo is not the only infrastructure which struggles with the lack of globally unique collection identifiers in the specimen record. Existing infrastructures such as the Global Registry of Scientific Collections (GrSciColl) also have trouble connecting specimens in GBIF with collections in GrSciColl.⁶ There is a possibility for a joint effort as multiple infrastructures would benefit from this additional specimen information.

Within the two accepted TDWG data standards, DwC and ABCD, there is already space available for a collection identifier. The recommendation to use a globally unique identifier, such as a GrSciColl identifier, is already part of the DWC documentation. For DWC, the term is called “collectionID”.⁷ For ABCD the location is less clear and might need a recommendation from the TDWG ABCD schema group.⁸

Latimer Core data model

Vital to the success of creating a generic interface for the Collection Description Dashboards is a generic data model. In the past years, there has been a lot of effort put into describing collections, resulting in the acceptance of Latimer Core as a Biodiversity Information Standard (Woodburn et al. 2022). This standard can be used to create a specific implementation of Latimer Core for the CDD. This specification can be based on the work done by DiSSCo UK and DiSSCo Flanders, described above. It needs to contain the vital collection metadata and leave room for more detailed information.

Connection with collection registries

There are several collection registries containing collection metadata. We would need a list of the registries we need to harvest information from. There might also be conflicting information between the different registries, a prioritisation of the registries is important. All required collection registries need to have a way through which they expose their data, e.g. an endpoint through which we can harvest.

In addition to DiSSCo harvesting information, the collection registries might be interested in additional information that is being provided by DiSSCo. Through DiSSCo’s event based setup, we can push new information to external systems. If there are collection registries interested in DiSSCo’s information, it would be good to set up a task to pinpoint what information and how DiSSCo can best supply it.

Authorisation management

As there has been an expressed need for users to be able to add additional collection metadata through DiSSCo. We need some kind of authorisation management: Who is authorised to supply this information? Can a user change metadata that has been received from a collection registry, or can they only add new metadata to the collection? These and other questions need to be answered before we can move towards implementing user provided information about the collection through DiSSCo. For the

⁶ For example, of the almost 9 million specimens available in GBIF from Naturalis Biodiversity Center, only 0.36% can be matched to a collection.

⁶ <https://scientific-collections.gbif.org/institution/0e919a55-08d3-4bd2-aec1-200858fafd92> (Visited 17-04-2024)

⁷ https://dwc.tdwg.org/list/#dwc_collectionID (Visited on 16-04-2024)

⁸ At https://dwc.tdwg.org/list/#dwc_collectionID the ABCD equivalence is given as [DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/SourceID](#). However, ABCD also contains a term called [Named Collection Or Survey](#) which might be more appropriate. (Visited on 16-04-2024)

implementation, we can reuse the existing DiSSCo Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI).

Generic vs specific requirements frontend

In this document, we have seen three different solutions for the Collection Description Dashboard, with each setup having a slightly different audience and requirements. If we want to make a generic European dashboard which can be customised to create specific CDDs, it needs to be clear what functionality needs to be part of the generic implementation and what needs to be part of specific solutions.

It would be good to have clear requirements for the generic implementation, including mock-ups. The current CDDs can probably be used as a starting point, as they already fulfil some user requirements.

5. Recap and next steps

The implementations presented by DiSSCo UK (2.2) and DiSSCo Flanders (2.3) offer recommendable solutions within their respective domestic context. These approaches provide advanced blueprints for the mobilisation of collection-level data such as digitization status data for DSArch (detailed in 3.2). Since the requirement of a local CDD deployment might introduce significant technical and organisational barriers for individual national nodes, a generic data delivery path involving a common CDD instance is included (Fig. 1) to foster mainstreaming of collection data in the framework of DSArch. Details such as the hosting organisation of the generic CDD instance cannot as yet be determined within MS 15, a close connection with the CETAF registry of collections⁹ is certainly sensible.

We therefore propose a resubmission regarding the outstanding organisational issues aligned with the submission of MS 16 (M12). Senckenberg will organise this involving the representatives of the CDD deployments (NHM, APM), DSArch (NBC) and the CETAF registry (RBINS).

However, we are of the view that the actual objective of MS3.2, the design of a *plan for integration of the Collection Digitisation Dashboard with the core infrastructure and connection with Latimer Core compatible data sources for collection descriptions*, is already broadly met in this report with respect to the technical approach.

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